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Analyzing and ranking of 5S Implementation Barriers in Industrial Organizations Using MOORA Method

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Abstract- In the current scenario execution of quality management (QM) practices as 5S has become the essential prerequisite to manufacturing managers (M). Effective implementation of 5S will result in a decent working environment in an organization. During the implementation process, manufacturing managers (M) experience different types of barriers in their organization. The main persistence of the current work is to identify and analyse the barriers affecting the implementation of 5S using Multi-Objective Optimization by Ratio Analysis (MOORA) approach. Finally, MOORA approach is used to rank the barriers according to their level of behaviour.

Key words - Quality management, 5S, Barriers, Ranking, MOORA

1. INTRODUCTION

Quality management technique practices like 5S, kaizen, total productive maintenance (TPM), total quality management (TQM) etc. are widely used by different types of industrial organizations in order to improve their performance. It is quite true that implementation of these practices has led into the survival of industrial organizations in the present cut-throat competitive environment scenario. Randhawa and Ahuja (2017) have considered 5S as a philosophy for attaining overall organization cleanliness and standardization at workplace in order to motivate the employees in an industry. According to Jaca et al., (2014) 5S is an effective and adequate technique that helps industries to initiate and achieve the continuous improvement process over time. 5S basically consists of five Japanese words used to keep the workplace

clean, organized, and efficient i.e. Seiri (Sort), Seiton (Set in Order), Seiso (Shine), Seiketsu (Standardize) Shitsuke (Sustain). Various authors also have conducted various studies for successful implementation of 5S technique in industries.

Agrahari et al. (2015) conducted a case study using the 5S methodology in a small-scale industry, showing its practical use and benefits. Similarly, Borbonio, J., & Chama Esteban, J. L. (2024) investigated the implementation of 5S methodology in a construction company warehouse and reported improvements in organization, efficiency, and safety through 5S practices. Mazur et al. (2024) also reported a case study focused on the implementation of a 5S program in a manufacturing industry, emphasizing improvements in productivity, efficiency and workplace discipline. Alcoba & Alcoba (2023) identified critical success factors for effective 5S system implementation in selected manufacturing companies, including human-related, material, and immaterial factors, and recommended a multi-dimensional approach to building and sustaining a 5S culture. Moreover, in this paper various obstacles have been highlighted during the 5S implementation. Bhavesh Kanabar et al. (2024) have also contributed in healthcare industries in terms of benefits like improved organization, staff motivation, cleanliness, and waste reduction. Mario Rojas et al. (2024) have used this approach in Smart interfaces to assist the operator in the context of Industry 4.0 with a 5S human-centric approach. Ibrahim and Sutrisno (2025) advocated that the successful application of 5S requires genuine

commitment from both top management and the employees working in the industrial organization.

The main aim of present work are as follows:

- To identify the key barriers affecting the implementation of the 5S methodology.
- To analyse the identified 5S implementation barriers using the MOORA method.
- To prioritize and rank the barriers based on their relative significance and impact.

II BARRIERS IN 5S IMPLEMENTATION

This part of the paper has barriers affecting the 5S operations which have been identified on the basis of extensive literature review. On the basis of several literature reviews such as Somers & Nelson (2004); Suárez-Barraza & Ramis-Pujol (2012); Agnieszka Grzelak (2024); Norman Alcoba & Rowena Alcoba (2023); Kanabar et al (2025); BV. Karthikeyan et al., (2025); Bhavesh Kanabar et al. (2024); Widen E. (2022); Zhang Ce et al. (2025); barriers mentioned in Table 1 were identified.

Table 1: Barriers in 5S implementation

S. No.	Barrier	Notation
1	Lack of support and commitment from top management.	C1
2	Communication gap	C2
3	Resource Limitations	C3
4	Inadequate training	C4
5	Poor strategic planning	C5
6	Insufficient feedback	C6
7	Weak Standardization	C7
8	Reluctance to adopt change	C8
9	Lack of workforce motivation	C9

III RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In the present research, the Multi-Objective Optimization by Ratio Analysis (MOORA) method has been employed to analyse the barriers to 5S implementation in manufacturing industries. Multi-objective optimization techniques is a systematic process of optimizing two or more conflicting criteria subject to defined constraints, as mentioned by Chakraborty (2011).

The MOORA technique has been extensively used in the literature to address complex decision-making problems in manufacturing and industrial environments due to its computational simplicity and robustness. For example, Akkaya et al. (2015) have used an integrated fuzzy AHP–fuzzy MOORA method to solve industrial engineering sector selection problems. Karande and Chakraborty (2012) utilized the fuzzy-MOORA method for ERP system selection. Similarly, Mangalan et al. (2016) utilize a weighted MOORA approach to determine the optimal warehouse location, while Stanujkic (2016) proposed an extension of the MOORA ratio system for group decision-making contexts, Moslem, S., & Çelikbilek, Y. (2020). Chauhan et al. (2022) also applied an integrated grey AHP-MOORA model for ameliorating public transport service quality. Hemant Sharma et al. (2022) have made Comparative analysis of ranking the lean supply chain enablers using MOORA and other MCDM methods. Sitio, S. L. M. (2025) has utilized this approach for Comparative analysis of MOORA and WASPAS methods for selecting the best supplier.

The steps involved in the MOORA analysis are as follows:

Step 1: Development of the decision matrix

Step 2: Normalize the decision matrix

Step 3: Identification of beneficial and non-beneficial attributes.

Step 4: Evaluation of the assessment value

Step 5: Establishment the ranking of variable

IV RANKING OF BARRIERS

After identifying the barriers to 5S implementation, these barriers were evaluated using the MOORA method. or this study, five managers from different manufacturing companies were selected because they had knowledge and experience in 5S practically implementation. On an average, these decision maker managers (M) had 12 years of work experience. They were requested to rate how difficult it is to handle each 5S barrier using a Likert scale from 1 to 5, where 1 means very low difficulty and 5 means very high difficulty. The ratings given by them are shown in Table 2.

Table 2: Data related to 5S rating

Barriers	M 1	M 2	M 3	M 4	M 5
C1	5	5	5	5	4

C2	3	4	3	4	4
C3	3	2	2	3	2
C4	4	5	4	4	3
C5	5	4	5	4	4
C6	4	4	4	5	4
C7	3	4	4	4	4
C8	3	3	2	3	3
C9	2	3	3	4	3

Subsequently collecting information from the manufacturing managers (M) related to data, the next step of the process is to normalize the data to make it dimensionless. Karande and Chakraborty, (2012) has developed the following normalization equation as used in table 2 for data purpose.

$$X_{ij}^* = \frac{x_{ij}}{\sum_{i=1}^m x_{ij}}$$

after making the data normalized through MOORA method, we added for beneficial factors and subtracted for non-beneficial factors using a formula as developed by Karande and Chakraborty (2012).

$$\text{Assessment value } (y_i) = \sum_{j=1}^g X_{ij}^* - \sum_{j=g+1}^n X_{ij}^*$$

Letter g indicates the number of beneficial factors and (n-g) indicates the number of non-beneficial factor

Table 2: Normalized data

Barr iers	M 1	M 2	M 3	M 4	M 5
C1	0.15706	0.14889	0.16152	0.17129	0.13903
C2	0.09777	0.11111	0.12665	0.11765	0.13121
C3	0.09824	0.06556	0.07452	0.09777	0.07061
C4	0.12765	0.14889	0.13121	0.13903	0.09777
C5	0.14889	0.12765	0.17129	0.13903	0.13121
C6	0.12765	0.14889	0.13903	0.14889	0.13121
C7	0.09777	0.11111	0.12765	0.13903	0.13121
C8	0.09824	0.06556	0.07061	0.09777	0.09777
C9	0.07452	0.14889	0.09777	0.13121	0.09824

Now, the score of each 5S barrier is calculated using the above formula. In this case, all the selected barriers values are treated as **non-beneficial factors** (i.e. lower values are better and higher values are worse). Table 3 Represent the calculated value of each barrier.

Table 3. Evaluation of the assessment value

Barriers	Assessment Value (sum)	Rank (Lower assessment value = Higher priority / Rank 1)
C1	0.77779	9
C2	0.58439	4
C3	0.40670	1
C4	0.64455	6
C5	0.71807	8
C6	0.68581	7
C7	0.60677	5
C8	0.45772	2
C9	0.49507	3

From the above table, it is revealed that Barrier C1 is having highest assessment value and having least critical barrier (Rank 9). similarly, C3 is the most critical barrier (Rank 1).

Finally, barriers were ranked on the basis of assessment value. The barriers having highest assessment value shows the high level of difficulty in managing them. Table 3 also shows the ranking of given barrier.

V CONCLUSION

The implementation of the 5S program leads to an improved working atmosphere and enhanced quality environment within an industry. However, similar to other quality management and continuous improvement initiatives, the successful adoption of 5S is often hindered by several barriers, including Lack of support and commitment from top management, Communication gap, Resource Limitations, Poor strategic planning, Insufficient feedback, Weak Standardization, Reluctance to adopt changes, Lack of workforce motivation, Inadequate training and poor planning. In the present study, the MOORA method has been employed to evaluate and rank the barriers

affecting 5S implementation. Compared with other multi-criteria decision-making techniques such as the Analytical Network Process (ANP), Analytical Hierarchy Process (AHP), and the Graph Theoretic Approach (GTA), the MOORA method is relatively simple, efficient, and easy to apply.

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